

Studies on the Complex Formation of Anhydrous Ti(III) Chloride with Primary Mono and Diamines

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Complexes of $TiCl_3$ with primary mono- and diamines have been prepared; their properties have been studied and their compositions determined.

George and Stähler¹ reported formation of a yellow emulsion when $TiCl_3$ was shaken with liquor ammonia, a part of which appeared to dissolve. Schumb and Sundstrom² observed $TiCl_3$ to combine with ammonia at a low temperature to form a hexammine, which on heating to 300° parted with 4 molecules of ammonia, a reactive black substance, probably a diammine, remaining behind. Hartmann *et al.*³ studied the complex formation of $TiCl_3$ with *i*-PrOH, dioxane, THF, acetylacetone, dimethyl formamide, MeOH, and EtOH from the aspect of a study of colour and constitution. Ehrlich and Siebert⁴ prepared addition compounds of titanium chloride with dimethyl formamide. By treating $TiCl_3$ with THF Pregaglia *et al.*⁵ obtained a blue crystalline precipitate. Of the formula $TiCl_3 \cdot 3 THF$ which, when heated with *n*-heptane, turned to a green precipitate of $TiCl_3 \cdot 2THF$. Fowles *et al.*⁶ obtained the complexes $TiCl_3 \cdot (NH_4X)NH_2R$ with $TiCl_3$ and $MeNH_2$ and $EtNH_2$, complexes of the type $TiCl_3 \cdot 3L$, $TiCl_3 \cdot 2L$, and $TiCl_3 \cdot L$ with 1,4-dioxane, 1,4-trioxane, morpholine, and ketones and $TiCl_3 \cdot 1,5 (CH_2OMe)_n$ with ethyl glycol dimethyl ether and also with *N*-methylmorpholine and methyl cyanide. With dimethyl and diethyl sulphides they obtained unstable complexes⁷ which decomposed on gentle heating.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to studying the formation of complex compounds of $TiCl_3$ with mono- and diamines as no work appeared to have been done on the subject.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were either of B.D.H.-A.R. quality or of E. Merck extra pure quality. Anhydrous $TiCl_3$ was prepared by reducing $TiCl_4$ using finely divided aluminium powder at 190° . The black mass formed was extracted with anhydrous ethyl acetate and filtered. It was analysed for purity. (Found: Ti, 31.25; Cl, 68.82. Calc. Ti, 31.07; Cl, 68.93%),

1. *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2200.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 596.

3. *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1950, 284, 163.

4. *Ibid.*, 1950, 303, 90.

5. *Ann. Chim. Rome*, 1959, 49, 1784.

6. U. S. Dept. Com., Office Tech. Serv., PB Dept., 1962, pp. 149, 423, 19.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 5673; 1954, 4963; *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, p. 368.

TABLE I

Amine	*Compound formed	Colour	M.P.	%Titanium		%Chlorine		%Org. matter	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
α -Naphthylamine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Dark mustard-yellow	280°d	8.79	9.08	20.24	20.16	N: 5.12	5.30
β -Naphthylamine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Do	260°	9.20	9.08	20.42	20.16	C: 54.12 H: 4.81	54.50 4.92
α -Aniline	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Do	208°	9.80	9.83	21.45	21.61	C: 44.08 H: 5.52	44.23 5.32
p "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Light violet	260°d	9.97	9.83	21.88	21.81	N: 5.61	5.73
m "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Mustard-yellow	230°	9.99	9.82	21.99	21.81	68.36	68.36
n-Toluidine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Black	210°	10.20	10.52	23.03	23.33	66.27	66.15
o "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Dirty colour	250°d	10.38	10.52	23.00	23.33	C: 47.51 H: 5.58	47.32 5.99
p "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Mustard-yellow	230°	10.64	10.52	23.44	23.33	N: 6.69	6.13
o-Phenetidine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Dark	200°	9.36	9.29	20.41	20.63	70.23	70.07
p "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Light violet	220°	9.50	9.29	20.35	20.63	N: 5.61	5.42
Aniline	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Mustard-yellow	250°	11.40	11.20	25.05	24.86	C: 44.05	44.61
Benzylamine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Dark mustard-yellow	280°	10.50	10.52	23.63	23.33	H: 5.42 C: 47.61	5.13 47.32
p-Tyldine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Me}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3 \cdot \text{NH}_2) \cdot \text{X}$	Mustard-yellow	250°	10.09	9.91	22.24	21.99	H: 5.41	5.69
p-Phenylamine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{X}$	Dark mustard-yellow	260°d	13.50	13.70	29.97	30.39	N: 5.52 C: 34.5	5.79 34.24
m "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{X}$	Dark	> 300°	13.94	13.70	30.22	30.39	H: 4.66	4.56
o "	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{X}$	Brick-red	260°	13.87	13.70	30.56	30.39	N: 8.10	7.99
Benzidine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{NH}_2)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{X}$	Dark	> 300°	11.51	11.26	25.10	24.99	55.67	55.91
o-Tolidine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{CH}_3\text{NH})_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4 \cdot \text{X}$	Mustard-yellow	> 300°	10.81	10.55	23.64	23.43	N: 6.32	6.56
o-Dimethidine	$\text{TiCl}_3 \cdot (\text{OH} \cdot \text{O} \cdot (\text{NH}_2)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3)_2 \cdot \text{X}$	Light brown	285°	10.09	9.87	22.90	21.90	65.55 N: 5.52	64.02 5.76

† denotes decomposition temperature.

* X denotes MeCO_2Et

Complexes were prepared by adding $TiCl_3$ solution in small quantities to the corresponding amine solution in ethyl acetate in such a way that the amine solution was in slight excess. It was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed with ethyl acetate free of the amine, and dried first between the folds of filter paper and then in a vacuum desiccator.

Titanium was estimated as TiO_2 and chlorine as $AgCl$ by Piria and Schiffs' method. In a few cases nitrogen was estimated by Dumas method and carbon and hydrogen by micro-analysis. IR spectrum of the complex of $TiCl_3$ with tolidine was also taken on the IR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer Co.) reading between 300 and 500.

General Properties.—The compounds are all coloured, fairly stable, and insoluble in organic solvents like CCl_4 , C_6H_6 , acetone, $CHCl_3$ etc. Some of them are, however, slightly soluble in ethyl acetate and ethanol. These dissolve in dilute mineral acids. The water extract responds to the test for chlorine, showing thereby that chlorine is either loosely attached or the compound undergoes hydrolysis.

When heated at 100° , it loses in weight corresponding to the loss of one molecule of ethyl acetate. On further heating, some of them show sharp melting points and the remaining melt with decomposition (Table I).

DISCUSSION

The results show that one molecule of $TiCl_3$ combines with two molecules of a primary mono-amine and one of a diamine. In all the cases one molecule of ethyl acetate also takes part in the complex formation, leading to the formation of $TiCl_3 \cdot 2A \cdot CH_3CO_2Et$ in the case of a primary monoamine and $TiCl_3 \cdot D \cdot CH_3CO_2Et$ in the case of a diamine, respectively.

Though titanium does not assume the inert gas configuration, the compounds are fairly stable, probably due to the symmetrical distribution of the ligands.

IR spectral study of the complex of $TiCl_3$ with tolidine (Fig. 1) shows peaks (Table II) corresponding to the different groups.

TABLE II

Wave numbers.	Corresponding groups.	Wave numbers.	Corresponding groups.
3332.424 cm^{-1}	N-H bond	1526.301 cm^{-1}	
2889.385	C-H stretch	1492.131	Ring vibration
1617.682		1459.456	
1597.009	N-H bond	1377.035	
		1232.710	C-N stretching vibration

Wave numbers corresponding to titanium chloride being between 300 and 500 could not be recorded.

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